

RESPONSE OF CYLINDRICAL COMPOSITE STRUCTURES TO UNDERWATER IMPULSIVE LOADING

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Abstract

The dynamic response of filament wound cylindrical composite structures subjected to underwater impulsive loads is analyzed. The analysis focuses on the effect of varying structural attributes and material properties on load-carrying capacity, deflection, energy dissipation and damage. The structural designs studied are monolithic composite structures and sandwich structures with foam cores of different relative densities and different radii. Underwater impulsive loads are generated using a novel experimental setup. The deflection and core compression are characterized using 2D Digital Image Correlation (DIC). The experiments are supported by fully dynamic numerical calculations which account for fluid-structure interactions and damage and failure mechanisms in the materials. For the same applied impulse, the monolithic cylindrical sections experience significant warping, delamination and cracking, while the sandwich structures experience significantly lower levels of damage. In the sandwich structures, as the core density increases, the transmitted impulse and overall damage also increase. Deflection and warping in the impulsively loaded region are influenced by the radius of curvature and material orientation. The results show that cylindrical sandwich structures have superior blast-resistance than cylindrical monolithic structures of equal mass with only relatively minor increases in wall thickness. The experiments, computations and structure-performance relations obtained offer approaches for designing structures with superior blast mitigating capabilities for sections in critical parts of ship structures like the keel, hull and pipes.

1. Introduction

Marine structures are designed to operate in hostile environments which involve corrosive sea water, hot and cold temperature extremes, transient dynamic loads like hull slamming, and complex three dimensional hydrodynamic load triaxialities. Additionally, naval structures are required to withstand weapons impacts and blast loads resulting from surface and underwater explosions. Recent assessments of marine structures have demonstrated that sandwich composites can provide good blast mitigation due to their high strength to weight ratios and high shear and bending resistances. Characterization of the behavior of composite materials and polymeric foams under impulsive loading is a prerequisite for the analysis and design of effective, blast resistant sandwich composites. Deformation and failure due to dynamic loading in layered materials such as composite laminates has been the subject of numerous investigations in recent years. Gas gun based impact loading has been successfully used to generate impulsive loading through water [1-3]. A major aspect of marine composite structures that has not been thoroughly investigated is the response of cylindrical composite structures to blast loads. The objective of the present work is to characterize the dynamic deformations and damage response of curved sandwich composites with different core densities but similar total masses subjected to high intensity underwater impulsive loads. The analysis focuses on the effect of varying structural attributes and material properties on load-carrying capacity, deflection, energy dissipation and damage.

This is a combined experimental and computational study. Computationally, the cohesive finite element method (CFEM) is employed to track the fracture processes. The major fracture mechanisms considered include interlaminar delamination between composite plies with different fiber orientations, intralaminar cracking, core cracking and core-face debonding. In the CFEM framework, there are two main approaches to resolve crack initiation and growth. One approach is to insert cohesive elements ahead of the crack tip as the crack grows [4]. This method can avoid the cohesive surface induced stiffness reduction of the overall model caused due to a finite stiffness of the cohesive traction-separation relation. However, this approach is computationally expensive and requires specific fracture initiation criteria. Another approach involves embedding cohesive surfaces along all finite element boundaries as an intrinsic part of the physical model [5, 6]. The constitutive behavior of bulk phases and cohesive surfaces are specified separately. Dynamic crack initiation and growth can be tracked using this framework. Additionally, proper choice of cohesive surface stiffness and finite element size can alleviate and minimize the cohesive surface induced stiffness reduction [7].

2. Experimental facility and diagnostics

Planar underwater impulses are generated using a novel experimental setup called the Underwater Shock Loading Simulator (USLS). The USLS consists of a projectile impact based impulsive loading mechanism and clamped and simply supported boundary conditions. The cylindrical structure is supported on a steel flange. This loading condition closely resembles that found in naval structures. A force transducer is mounted on the flange to measure impulses transmitted. The location of material failure in this configuration allows accurate time-resolved measurements using high-speed digital imaging. Specifically, high-speed digital imaging and digital image correlation enables the study of deflection, face wrinkling, core face debonding, core compression, core shear cracking and rupture and their dependence on load intensity and core characteristics. This experimental setup is shown in Fig. 1.

The USLS can generate impulsive loads with peak pressures within the range of 40-250 MPa, which

resembles those created by underwater explosions. Fig. 2 shows the pressure histories of underwater impulses corresponding to different projectile velocities.

Fig. 1 Sectional view of Underwater Shock Loading Simulator (USLS) showing the setup for high speed digital imaging and digital image correlation analysis of the response of impulsively loaded cylindrical sandwich structures.

Fig. 2 Measured experimental pressure histories in the water chamber for four different projectile velocities.

3. Materials

The composite specimens are constructed with glass fiber reinforced plastic with two winding angles $[45^\circ]$ and $[-45^\circ]$. The wall thickness of monolithic cylindrical specimens is 5.5 mm. For the sandwich structure, the outer face is 3.5 mm thick, the inner face is 2.5 mm thick and the sandwich core is 10 mm thick. The core material is Divinycell HP100 PVC foam manufactured by DIAB Inc. [8]. Fig. 3 shows the different components of a filament wound composite cylinder. The sandwich structure is

manufactured by cutting the PVC foam into the required segments, inserting into concentric composite cylinders and impregnating the assembly with polyester resin. The inside surfaces of the cylindrical specimens are painted with an enamel spray to improve reflectivity for high-speed photography.

Fig. 3 Components of filament-wound, cylindrical fiberglass structure with $[45^\circ]/[-45^\circ]$ orientations.

4. Numerical Modeling

Finite element simulations using the experimental conditions and independently measured material properties are conducted to support the experiments and gain insight into the response of the structures. The simulations account for the FSI effect at the water composite interface, shear cracking and fragmentation in the core, matrix cracking and fiber failure in the faces, and core face interfacial debonding. Both the bulk composite and PVC foam follow an isotropic linear elastic constitutive relation. Cohesive elements are specified between all bulk element boundaries in the glass-reinforced polyester as well as PVC foam. The cohesive elements allow for damage initiation and development. For the zero-thickness cohesive elements, a bilinear cohesive law is adopted to govern traction-separation behavior. A schematic representation of the bilinear traction-separation law is shown in Fig. 4. Loading initially proceeds from point A to B, at which point softening occurs with

increasing strain until failure at a separation of δ . Because it is not physically meaningful for compressive tractions to contribute to damage initiation, only tensile normal tractions are considered in the damage initiation rule. Damage initiated and failure in the interfaces follow the mixed-mode fracture criterion [9]. Details about the CFEM approach presented here can be found in [5, 7, 10].

After failure of the cohesive elements, contact between bulk elements leads to frictional sliding. The surfaces that are fractured are identified as potential contact regions and master and slave surface designations are assigned to the corresponding bulk element faces. When the surfaces come in contact with one another, the Coulomb friction law governs the interfacial frictional force. The coefficient of friction is 0.6, which is typical for composite sliding [11].

CFEM models with cohesive traction-separation behavior with finite initial stiffness have two competing requirements on element size. The upper bound requires that the element size must be small enough to accurately resolve stress distribution inside cohesive zones at crack tips. The lower bound requires the cohesive surface induced stiffness reduction be minimal such that wave speed in the solid is not significantly affected. For the current analysis, the element size $50 \mu\text{m}$ and is calculated using the criteria specified in [7].

Fig. 4 Bilinear traction-separation law for cohesive elements.

A Lagrangian formulation is adopted to simulate wave propagation in water. It captures the exponentially decaying pressure waves and

cavitation at the fluid structure interface. The response of water is described by the Mie-Gruneisen equation of state.

5. Results

5.1 Experimental results

Structural attributes, loading intensities and constituent properties determine the overall fracture behavior through the activation of different fracture mechanisms which include delamination, interlaminar crack growth, intralaminar cracking, core-face debonding and fragmentation. In response to the impulsive loads specified in Fig. 2, a stress wave propagates through the curved composite laminate. The stress wave propagation is initially perpendicular to incident wave and follows the curvature of the cylindrical structure. Fig. 5 shows high speed photographs of a monolithic composite cylinder 5 mm in thickness subjected to an underwater impulsive load corresponding to a projectile velocity of 50 m/s. The high-speed photographs capture the dynamic deformation and warping in the composite cylinder. Figure 6 shows the post-test photographs of loaded specimens. Visual inspection reveals that delamination and fiber and matrix rupture are the major failure mechanisms

in the cylindrical monolithic composite structure. Delamination is observed through the thickness in the filament wound plies while fiber and matrix cracking is observed on the inner and outer surfaces of the composite. For a similar incident impulse, the monolithic cylindrical sections experience significantly greater warping, delamination and cracking as compared to sandwich structures. In sandwich structures, the presence of a PVC foam core provides resilience and flexural stiffness and enhances the blast resistance of the structure and consequently, reduces delamination and interlaminar cracking. On the impulse side, the outer face experiences interlaminar cracking and fiber-matrix debonding and the inner face is relatively undamaged. Permanent core compression is not extensive and is restricted to the HP100 foam close to the loaded area.

Overall, the following damage modes are observed in both structures:

- delamination and interlaminar cracking
- intralaminar cracking, matrix cracking and fiber rupture
- structural deformation and warping
- core compression and partial recovery.

Figure 5 High speed photographs of a monolithic composite structure subjected to an impulsive load generated by a projectile velocity of $V_0=50$ m/s.

Figure 6 Post-mortem photographs of impulsively loaded cylindrical composite structure. Delamination and matrix cracking can be observed. The delaminated region is outlined in the impulse and support side pictures.

Figure 7 Post-mortem photographs of an impulsively loaded cylindrical sandwich composite structure. The delaminated region is outlined in the impulse and support side pictures. The areas of delamination on the impulse and support sides as well interlaminar cracking are both significantly smaller in the sandwich structure.

5.2 Validation of numerical model

Results from the numerical analysis of the response of the cylindrical composite structures to localized blasts provides insight and a more in-depth understanding of the failure modes, damage initiation and growth, velocity transfer and energy dissipation. The cohesive finite element framework provides a means of evaluating the blast resistance of composite structures through explicit simulation of deformation processes in the structure. The boundary conditions applied to the model represent those in the experiments. The conditions closely resemble a cylindrical structure anchored to a larger structure, which is common for submarines, underwater pipelines and missiles. As in experiments, a planar underwater impulsive wave is incident on the side of the cylinder simulating a "side-on" loading condition.

Figure 8 shows the stress wave propagation in a monolithic cylindrical composite structure. Figure 9 shows a sequence of magnified images illustrating

the damage initiation and growth process. As the stress wave propagates through the composite structure, the bonds between successive laminates fail and delamination occurs at $t=200 \mu\text{s}$. When the interlaminar crack jumps from one interface to another, it inevitably leads to matrix cracking and intralaminar crack growth. Due to the dynamic nature of this process, buckling initiates in the composite structure and causes cracking and failure in the laminates as observed at $t=600 \mu\text{s}$. As deformation progresses, the intralaminar cracks link together to create a shear band along which the entire laminate undergoes failure and rupture.

Figure 10 shows a comparison of experimentally measured and computationally predicted displacement and velocity profiles of the inner surface of an impulsively loaded monolithic composite cylinder. The simulation predicts a lower value of permanent displacement and velocity but the final value is within 5% of the experimentally measured value.

Figure 8 Stress wave propagation, deformation and failure in a cylindrical monolithic composite structure at different times.

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Figure 9 Damage initiation and growth in cylindrical composite structure under impulsive loading. Delamination initiates at $t = 200 \mu\text{s}$, and buckling occurs at $t = 400 \mu\text{s}$. At $t = 600 \mu\text{s}$, kinking occurs at the inner surface and causes cracking followed by rupture and fragmentation.

Figure 10 Comparison of experimentally measured and computationally predicted displacement and velocity of the inner face in a monolithic cylindrical composite subjected to an impulsive load corresponding to $V_0 = 50\text{m/s}$.

5.3 Numerical results

The time histories of energy dissipation in the monolithic structure are shown in Figure 11(a-c).

Dynamic compression in the bulk composite is the primary dissipation mechanism in the earlier stages of deformation, as the matrix absorbs the input

energy and accommodates the imposed deformation. Accordingly, delamination initiates soon after the onset of the impulsive load as the interlaminar interfaces fail due to shear stresses. The failed surfaces interact with each other causing friction.

The frictional dissipation in the structure is initially significantly lower than fracture work but as the fracture surfaces interact with each other, frictional dissipation surpasses both strain energy as well

Figure 11 Energy dissipation through dynamic deformation, fracture and friction of failed surfaces as a function of time for the monolithic cylinder.

as fracture work. Figure 11(b) shows the energy dissipated due to the creation of new crack surfaces while Figure 11(c) shows energy dissipation due to friction between failed surfaces.

Figure 12 shows the distributions of stress at different times for a cylindrical sandwich composite subjected to an underwater impulsive load. Initially, the stress wave travels through the outer face, creating highly stressed regions at the core-outer face interface. The core undergoes significant compression and minor cracking. Although large scale delamination is caused due to the incident loads, intralaminar cracking does not initiate. Due to the absence of intralaminar cracking, there is no structural rupture in spite of the reduction in overall strength due to delamination. This indicates that in addition to improve the overall stiffness of the cylindrical structure, the PVC foam core also improves blast mitigation by alleviating some of the effects of flexural wave propagation in the composite sections. For similar incident impulsive loads, sandwich composites outperform monolithic composite.

Figure 13 shows the time histories of displacement and velocity for the inner and outer face of a cylindrical sandwich composite structure subjected

to an impulsive load corresponding to $V_0 = 50\text{m/s}$. Initially, the core is compressed and the outer face travels faster than the inner face. As deformation progresses and the load is transmitted to the inner face, the inner face acquires velocity and travels in a direction opposite to the impulsive loading direction.

The evolution of elastic strain energy, fracture work and frictional dissipation as functions of time is shown in Figure 14. The energy expenditure in the entire structure is shown in Figure 14(a). Elastic strain energy is higher in the initial stages of deformation. As damage initiates in the form of delamination, intralaminar cracking and core cracking, the magnitude of energy dissipated in formation of cracks increases monotonically. With an increase in overall fracture, the interactions between fractured surfaces also increases leading to high frictional dissipation. The fracture work and frictional dissipation both surpass the elastic strain energy. Figure 14(b) shows the energy dissipated due to the creation of crack surfaces. The outer face, which is in close proximity to the impulsive load, undergoes the highest fracture work while the core and inner face exhibit similar energy dissipation characteristics. Figure 15 shows the time histories of energy spent on creating cracks in different

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components of the sandwich structure. Clearly, damage initiation and growth is affected by material

orientation, interfacial effects and core cracking.

Figure 12 Distribution of stress at different times for a composite sandwich structure subjected to an underwater impulsive wave.

Figure 13 Numerically calculated displacement and velocity as functions of time for the inner and outer faces of a cylindrical sandwich composite structure subjected to an impulsive load corresponding to $V_0 = 50\text{m/s}$.

Figure 14 Energy dissipated in a cylindrical sandwich composite structure subjected to underwater impulsive loading.

Figure 15 Fracture work in different components of a cylindrical sandwich composite structure subjected to underwater impulsive loading.

Figure 16 Comparison of total energy dissipation in monolithic and sandwich structures subjected to similar impulsive loads.

6. Conclusion

The response of filament-wound cylindrical composite structures is investigated numerically and experimentally. The materials of choice are glass-fiber reinforced polymer and structural PVC foam,

commonly found in marine construction. Underwater impulsive loading experiments are conducted at a fixed stand-off distance with impulsive loads similar to those observed in an underwater blast. Fluid-structure interaction is captured using an equation of state for water. A

novel cohesive finite element framework is implemented to accurately track the various deformation mechanisms in composite structures. This framework is able to accurately depict interlaminar delamination and cracking, fiber and matrix damage, intralaminar and translaminar cracking and friction between newly created surfaces.

Experiments show that monolithic and sandwich composite structures exhibit multiple competing failure modes include core compression, delamination, core-face debonding, translaminar cracking, matrix and fiber rupture. Maximum core compression was observed on the side nearest to the blast load, indicating that the outer face deformed significantly into the core before recovering. For similar total masses, the sandwich structure provided considerably superior blast mitigation as compared to the monolithic structure. Overall, filament wound cylindrical structures exhibited good resiliency under blast loading. While the monolithic structure showed signs of severe internal damage and warpage, the sandwich structure was relatively unwarped and recovered most of the original geometry.

Numerical simulations carried out in this analysis provide an insight into the deformation mechanisms and energy dissipation in the composite structures. Simulations show that interlaminar delamination is an important damage mechanism. Delamination contributes to only 20% of the overall fracture work and ~ 5% of total energy dissipation and it is the driving force for other failure modes in the composite. Delamination precipitates the formation of intralaminar and translaminar cracks which lead to catastrophic failure and rupture. Additionally, interlaminar cracks span across large sections of the composite while fiber and matrix cracking is restricted to small regions close to the loading area. Simulations reveal that friction between cracked surfaces is major source of energy expenditure and is comparable in magnitude to fracture work and strain energy. Cracking and friction at the core face interface is found to be negligible in all cases. This can be attributed to the presence of the low density foam core which does not provide a significant resistance to shear deformation.

Computations reveal that cylindrical sandwich structures outperform monolithic structures significantly. The sandwich core helps mitigate the effects of high pressures on the cylindrical structure. Figure 16 shows a comparison of energy dissipation in the form of fracture, friction and elastic strain. Results indicate that for a similar applied impulse, the sandwich structure dissipates almost twice as much energy as the monolithic structure. This is primarily because of the presence of a compressible foam core and a thinner outer face which contribute to higher elastic strain and fracture work respectively.

The cohesive finite element model provides a unique approach to track the different damage modes in curved composites. Although the numerical model captures the essential deformation mechanisms, it slightly overestimates the effects of matrix cracking and rupture. Therefore, the cohesive element properties need to be recalibrated to ensure accurate representation of experimentally observed failure characteristics. Additionally, the effect of core density on dynamic response of sandwich structures is an important aspect that needs to be investigated.

The numerical capability can be utilized to design and optimize curved fiber composite structures subjected to side loading in navy vessels. In such an approach, the newly developed numerical scheme can provide an accurate and physically realistic representation of experimental results. This numerical scheme can be used for a variety of materials and structural geometries.

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7. References

1. Espinosa, H.D., S. Lee, and N. Moldovan, *A novel fluid structure interaction experiment to investigate deformation of structural elements subjected to impulsive loading*. Experimental Mechanics, 2006. **46**(6): p. 805-824.
2. Latourte, F., et al., *Failure mechanisms in composite panels subjected to underwater impulsive loads*. Journal of the Mechanics

- and Physics of Solids, 2011. **59**(8): p. 1623-1646.
3. McShane, G.J., et al., *Dynamic rupture of polymer-metal bilayer plates*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 2008. **45**(16): p. 4407-4426.
 4. Pandolfi, A. and M. Ortiz, *An efficient adaptive procedure for three-dimensional fragmentation Simulations*. Engineering with Computers, 2002. **18**(2): p. 148-159.
 5. Zhai, J., V. Tomar, and M. Zhou, *Micromechanical simulation of dynamic fracture using the cohesive finite element method*. Journal of Engineering Materials and Technology-Transactions of the Asme, 2004. **126**(2): p. 179-191.
 6. Xu, X.P. and A. Needleman, *Numerical Simulations of Fast Crack-Growth in Brittle Solids*. Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, 1994. **42**(9): p. 1397-&.
 7. Tomar, V., J. Zhai, and M. Zhou, *Bounds for element size in a variable stiffness cohesive finite element model*. International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering, 2004. **61**(11): p. 1894-1920.
 8. DIAB Inc., S.D., DeSoto, Texas 75115, USA
http://www.diabgroup.com/europe/literature/e_pdf_files/man_pdf/H_man.pdf Accessed 5 May 2011.
 9. Kenane, M. and M.L. Benzeggagh, *Characterization of Mixed Mode Delamination Growth and Thresholds*. Damage and Fracture Mechanics, 2009: p. 523-530.
 10. Minnaar, K. and M. Zhou, *A novel technique for time-resolved detection and tracking of interfacial and matrix fracture in layered materials*. Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, 2004. **52**(12): p. 2771-2799.
 11. Schon, J., *Coefficient of friction of composite delamination surfaces*. Wear, 2000. **237**(1): p. 77-89.